

CHAPTER 5. RISE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADE
FROM THE 3RD TO THE 7TH CENTURIES A.D.

We have seen in the previous chapter that during the first and second centuries A.D., the period of The Periplus and of Pliny, the Gulf was something of a backwater beside the major trade routes of Asia.

Western contact with China was almost exclusively overland. The Parthians, with their traditional capitals on the edge of the Central Asian steppe, were well situated to handle the overland trade with the Han and had a near monopoly in the supply of Chinese silks to the Mediterranean. The role the sea lanes played in transporting Chinese products was almost certainly negligible. Indian and South-east Asian spices and other products were carried in Egyptian, Axumite, or South Arabian boats up the Red Sea to the Roman world. The products of South Arabia were transported by caravan on the famous incense route.

The role of the Persian Gulf seems to have been more modest. Omana, near the entrance of the Gulf, carried on small scale entrepôt activities, and although Jews and Palmyrenes, among others, sailed to India from the kingdom of Mesene at the head of the Gulf, the extent of maritime trade by contemporary, and especially by later, standards was small. Indeed, incense and spices were

brought to Gerrha, the most notable merchant city of the Gulf, not by sea, but by caravan across Arabia.

By the eighth or ninth century the whole commercial picture had changed. The normal route to China was no longer overland and the trade of the Red Sea was of considerably less importance than that of the Gulf. Instead, cities in the Persian Gulf which were totally dominated by maritime trade, such as Sirāf and Suhār, figured prominently in a greatly expanded Asian trade, frequently sending ships as far afield as Madagascar and Canton. It will be attempted in the next two chapters to examine the conditions under which the commercial position of the Gulf changed so radically. The period from the accession of the Sasanians, and especially from the 5th century A.D. till the 8th to 9th centuries is of greatest importance in this study. For it was at this time that the maritime trading cities which flourished in the^c Abbāsīd period and thereafter first took shape, and thus one might expect that a detailed study would provide evidence on the primary factors of their commercial function and of capital formation.*

In this chapter then, an attempt will be made first to examine the evidence for the commercial situation in the Gulf during the Sasanian period (224-649 A.D.),¹ and then to study the changing patterns of western Indian Ocean trade and the role of Gulf merchants there.

* Problems and theory of trade are discussed in Chapter 1.

In the succeeding chapter the evidence for the initiation of direct interoceanic trade as a normal practice will be examined in some detail. For it will be seen that the fortunes of the great Abbasid entrepôts seemed to be based on a carrying trade not just to India, but to the Far East and even to China, the largest single market of the Middle Ages. It is of primary importance then in a study of the maritime cities to determine at what stage in their development direct sailing to the Far East became common, and to establish if this was the staple, or merely the most exotic (and thus the most described), of their maritime contacts.

Unfortunately Gulf history during the Sasanian period is extremely poorly documented. Unlike its rival, the Roman Empire, the Sasanian Empire was totally absorbed by the Muslim Arab invaders. Thus, in the 9th and 10th centuries while the scribes of Byzantium were actively preserving their Greek heritage for posterity,² Islamic scholars with few exceptions were more concerned with the background and genealogies of tribal Arabia than in preserving the ancient histories of Persia. Even the Zoroastrian establishment, which might have been expected to preserve the records of its rulers was persecuted and weak, and has kept few records of its ancient greatness.

Only a small number of historical sources are preserved in Pahlavi, the language of the dynasty. There are a handful of rock

and stone inscriptions of which that of Shāhpūr on the Ka'ba-i Zardusht at Naqsh-i Rostam and that on the altar at Paikali are the most important.³ Original documentary sources are rare. Even the great majority of the Sasanian Avesta is lost and the theological or moral tales which survive elsewhere are of little historical value.⁴ Indeed, only two documentary sources in Pahlavi were of primary use in this study. The first, the Karnāma-i Ardashīr i Papakan is a romance history of Ardashīr I, the founder of the dynasty. The account is written in a heroic, semi-mythical genre but it does have the merit that it was probably originally composed in the 3rd century, shortly after the events it describes, though the version which has survived probably dates from the 6th century.⁵ The second source, the Shāhristān-i Iran is a list of the provinces and cities of the Empire, with a little information about each. It is extremely brief, but it is of importance since it seems to be essentially Sasanian in date, providing information of the 6th century, even though the version which has survived has certain additions from as late as the 8th century A.D.⁶

Similar information to the Shāhristān-i Iran occurs in the Geography attributed to Moses of Chorene, the Armenian historian of the 5th century. Several scholars have doubted the attribution to Moses, and have suggested the Geography was composed as late as the 7th century. More recently a 5th century date has been accepted for the original composition, despite 6th and 7th century

interpolations. The Geography has survived in two distinct redactions, the "long" version and the "abbreviated" version, each containing some original material not in the other.⁷

Besides this Armenian source, Roman and Byzantine histories provide glimpses of the Persian Gulf and of Sasanian maritime activities incidental to their accounts of Byzantine and Sasanian military and commercial rivalries. Ammianus Marcellinus in the 4th century and Procopius in the 6th are the most helpful sources.⁸ Two of the Greek sources stand out. For although neither describes the Gulf, they record voyages in the western Indian Ocean, one based on a first hand account and the other by the traveller himself.

The first is that of an anonymous Theban scholasticus in the middle of the 4th century. His account formed the basis of a Greek text attributed to Palladius of Helenopolis which is available in a large number of different versions, and also in a Latin fragment attributed to St. Ambrose.⁹ Winstedt, who was familiar with only a single version dismissed it as "little better than a fairy tale,"¹⁰ but some recent scholars have accepted it.¹¹ J. D. M. Derrett edited two versions of the text in 1961,¹² and it is clear from his research that although the fragment was probably written by neither Palladius nor Ambrose, it does record an actual journey.¹²

The second traveller is Cosmas, known as Indicopleustes (the Indian navigator). His Geography is lost and his only surviving work, The Christian Topography (second quarter of the 6th century) is more a religious tract than a travel account. In it he sets out "to refute from Scripture and common sense the impious pagan cosmography according to which the world is a sphere"¹³ and the centre of the heavens. He is in fact the Father of Mediaeval Geography and Beazley wrote of his work "at least it is a monument of infinite, because quite unconscious humour".¹⁴ Despite this unprepossessing background Cosmas is a primary source of great importance. He was a merchant before becoming a monk, and had sailed on the Mediterranean, the Red Sea, and even the Gulf. He had travelled through Ethiopia and had visited India and Ceylon. Some geographical fragments, particularly concerning Ethiopia, India, and Ceylon appear in The Christian Topography.¹⁵

A considerable quantity of Nestorian material in Syriac has survived. For the most part these are of strictly theological interest, but a few provide valuable incidental information. Principle among these are the Acts of Synods and lists of bishops who attended which were published by J. Chabot in Synodicon Orientale.¹⁶ A few official letters are also preserved.¹⁷ Other Nestorian sources, such as the Chronicle of Seert, written in Arabic in the 11th century, provide a few insights on life in the Gulf under the Sasanians.¹⁸

The Chinese Annales provide some information on western Indian Ocean trade, but as will be seen, this probably dates from the 1st century A.D., and is misleading in any case.¹⁹ Shortly after the Hejira, Hsue Tsiang visited North-west India and briefly describes Iran, though unfortunately he never travelled west of India.²⁰

The contemporary sources make up only a portion of our evidence. The major documentation for events in the Sasanian period are the early Islamic historians of the 9th to 11th centuries A.D., writing at least two centuries after the death of the last Sasanian ruler. Principle among them are al-Ṭabarī, al-Dīnawarī, Ḥamza al-Isfahānī, al-Bal^camī, al-Mas^cūdī, al-Tha^calībī, and to some extent Firdausī.²¹ * Their accounts are based above all on redactions of Pahlavi documents which survived during the early Islamic period and which were translated into Arabic by savants such as Ibn al-Muqaffa^c (first half of the 8th century)²² The most important of these sources were the Book of Kings, the Khvadhaynāma, the Āyennāma, translated in several thousand folios by Ibn al-Muqaffa^c, and the Gāhnāma, such as the one Mas^cūdī consulted at Ištakhr illustrated with miniatures of the Sasanian rulers.²³ These original documents were probably of restricted value in the first place, since all appear to have been written from the view point of the Zoroastrian clergy and the higher nobility, but we are greatly impoverished by the loss.²⁴

* For simplicity the Arabic articles are hereafter omitted.

None of the historians who excerpted them and whose works survive seem to have read the original Pahlavi. They depended on translations* into Arabic or Persian. Most of these were probably simply elaborations of existing translations. Thus Ḥamza, whose history is an important source noted that there were at least twenty translations of the Khvadhaynama available, but no two were in agreement. Recent scholars even consider that the Book of the Kings used by Firdausī was not a Persian translation from the Pahlavi, but derived from the same Arabic recension on which the historians depended. By Firdausī's time Ardashīr I had been dead 700 years.²⁵

The documentary sources then, though they range over a wide field, are poor and rather few. So, if the reconstruction of events on the Gulf during the Sasanian period seems to be on little information, it is not necessarily a sign of lack of contemporary interest in the Gulf, but rather an indication of the poverty of the sources.

In many cases the historical evidence has been clarified by the use of archaeological survey work, the principles of which were outlined in the Second Chapter. The archaeological data is fundamentally based on the determination of the date and distribution of certain pottery types. These are discussed in Appendix I, but

* I am only too aware that the historical portion of this study is mostly based on the use of translations and not on first hand examination of the sources. So my strictures on the early Islamic sources might in places apply to the present study.

it is relevant here to summarize the evidence for the archaeological dating.

The excavations at Sīrāf, which are the basis for almost all subsequent pottery chronology, unfortunately are of little assistance for any period before 803-804 A.D.. Although there was undoubtedly a considerable Sasanian settlement at Sīrāf, stratified deposits of Sasanian material are so small that the excavator feels unable, at the present stage of excavation, to positively identify any Sasanian pottery types, because of the possible contamination with much earlier residual material.²⁶

Fortunately there is some securely dated material from Mesopotamia. Enormous quantities of Partho/Sasanian material have been excavated in Mesopotamia and Khūzistān. However, almost all have come from the upper layers of much earlier sites, and were not dug with sufficient stratigraphic care to have much value for dating.²⁷ Currently the Italian mission at Seleucia/Ctesiphon is doing much to remedy this. Their excavations at Choche are producing material which, on the basis of coin finds and stratigraphic excavation can be securely dated between the 3rd and the 5th centuries A.D..²⁸ I have not personally examined this material to compare it with finds from the Gulf, but am grateful to Dr. Venco Riccardi who is in charge of the pottery from Choche for her examination of my pottery and identification of Gulf types which most closely

relate to those at Choche. Dr. Riccardi has also published some grave groups from Tell Mahuz in northern Mesopotamia, which provide confirmatory information.²⁹ However, parallels with the Choche material does not extend beyond the glazed pottery, nor are they very helpful for areas as far away as Kirmān province.

For the coarse wares and for the entrance to the Gulf, the excavations at Tepe Yahyā are of paramount importance. The excavator cautiously dates both his Levels I and IA (each represents major building periods) in the bracket 0 to 500 A.D.. There are no coins, but a fragment of inscription, two carbon dates, and a characteristic Gayomard seal are from these levels.³⁰ With the exception of one of the carbon dates, which was from Level IA, these items are from Level I, and all fall into the Early Sasanian (225-500) period. Mr. Humphries, who is working on the material from the upper levels at Tepe Yahyā has been kind enough to tell me which pottery types are represented only in Level I,³¹ and these almost certainly fall into the 200 to 500 A.D. bracket, although it is unknown how much longer they continued in use beyond this.

The late Sasanian period presents serious problems. There is no excavated material from Mesopotamia or the Gulf between c. 500 and c. 750. Thus the dating of late Sasanian material is less secure than for any other period of this study. It is felt that a single pottery type can be used as diagnostic. This is a most

distinctive glazed ware with bifurcating rim. It is not found at Choche, nor in Seleucia, nor any of the large bodies of Parthian pottery from Mesopotamia, and is also absent from Hira, Sāmarā, and other collections of Islamic types. It is, however, distributed in great quantities on the surface of sites all over the Gulf, and as far as the area of Choche itself. If it were before 500 it would surely have been found in the Italian excavations or in the material elsewhere of Parthian date.³¹ If, on the other hand, it dated from after 800 A.D. it would undoubtedly be found at Sīrāf, and probably also in the Mesopotamian excavations of that date. Apparently it falls between the two, and since it was totally out of use by the date of the construction of the Masjid-i Jāmi^c ("The Great Mosque") at Sīrāf in 803-804, might be identified as dating from c. 500-c. 750, though this identification must remain provisional until verified by excavation.

A final dated pottery type which is found on the Gulf in small numbers is a superb Red Polished Ware reported from India. It is common in excavations there (see sherd drawings, Fig. 7 D-F and distribution map, Fig. 9) and has been dated on the evidence of coins and other material to the 1st to 4th centuries A.D., which indicates a Parthian as well as an early Sasanian date.³³

Late Sasanian pottery from inland Fārs and Kirmān where Gulf types were not distributed can be dated by similar techniques.

The distinctive type is a range of burnished bowls with pointed rims which are found in late Sasanian or very early Islamic contexts at Naqsh-i Rostam, Qasr-i Abū Nasr, Level IV of the Takht at Pasargadae, and the upper levels at Tall-i Malyān.³⁴ These types are never found in contexts with pottery dateable from Sirāf to the 9th century, which is found at nearby Istakhr,³⁵ and although they are common on surface sites close to Tepe Yahya, do not appear in this excavation.³⁶ These bowl probably represent a horizon from c. 500 to c. 750. The early Sasanian horizon from Fars represents more of a problem, and can only be very tentatively identified, so it is not indicated on the distribution map (Fig. 4) for the Sasanian period.³⁷

These then are the basic sources on which the study of the growth of trade during the Sasanian period can be based. The scantiness of the historical information has been regretted by many scholars,³⁸ and it is hoped that by combining and elucidating them with the archaeological data a coherent picture will be seen to emerge.

In 224 the last Parthian ruler, Artabanus, was dead. The new ruler of Iran, Ardashīr, son of Papak and grandson of Sasan inaugurated a dynasty which was to achieve a stability the Parthians never attained. From the start the change in dynasty marked a change in the geographical outlook of the state. Although the

later Parthians had left their traditional capitals in Qumis and Khurāsān, their empire still looked northwards toward the land routes and the steppes.³⁹ The Sasanians, however, had strong religious and traditional connections with Fārs and southern Iran. Their capital was firmly established at Ctesiphon, accessible to the Gulf down the Tigris, and royal residences were often established in Fārs, within reach of the Gulf.⁴⁰

Perhaps the most suggestive indication of the change of geographical emphasis was the alteration of the official language from Parthian to Pahlavi, the dialect of the northern provinces and of the steppe, to Sasanian Middle Persian, the language of Fārs.⁴¹ In more concrete terms it will be suggested that the Sasanians had a particular interest in the Gulf and in its security, and that huge sums of money were invested in development projects on or near its littoral in Iraq, Khūzistān, Fārs, and Arabia.

Ardashīr, the founder of the dynasty, began the process. Initially he subdued the kingdom of Mesene which had maintained a semi-independent existence at the head of the Gulf under the Parthians, and crushed the petty princelings of Fārs and of the coast.⁴² Secondly, he expressed his concern with the Gulf area in more concrete terms. He was a great builder of cities, and according to various sources, no fewer than twenty-three were founded or refounded in his reign.⁴³ Although not all are identifiable, at

least one half of those that are were ports on the Gulf itself, or on the navigable lower courses of the rivers of Khūzistān and Mesopotamia.

In Khūzistān the new cities of Hurmuzd Ardashīr and Khujistān Wajar were built at what was later Sūq al-Ahvāz, and Bam Hurmuz was founded to the south.⁴⁴ Near the mouth of the Shatt al-^cArab, the great water route to Ctesiphon, the Sasanian capital, the maritime trading ports of Charax and Furat of Maisān were refounded as Astarabād Ardashīr and Bahman Ardashīr, and a new city, Wahasht Ardashīr was built.⁴⁵ On the coast of Fārs, Rēv Ardashīr (which I locate on the Būshahr peninsula), Bokht Ardashīr (probably also on the same peninsula), and Kudjarān Ardashīr were established.⁴⁶

Ardashīr sought to extend his power further, to the south coast of the Gulf, and led an expedition in person against the Arabs of al-Bahrayn. Their major fortress fell after the suicide of the Arab king Sanutruq, and a new Sasanian city was built in its place to consolidate the conquest.⁴⁷ The city, which was called Batn Ardashīr because its walls were supposed to have been built of alternate layers of bricks and Arab bodies, was located on the Arabian coast opposite Bahrain Island and in the area of the trading city of Gherra, which it came to supercede.⁴⁸ Ardashīr's expedition to al-Bahrayn might even have been the first Sasanian naval venture. For one of our sources mentions that Ardashīr set

out from Gūr, while an attack by land would almost certainly have been organized from Iraq.⁴⁹ There is no specific mention though, that it was a maritime assault.

However, the most expressive information on the state of the Gulf at the end of the Parthian period and the effect of the change of dynasty on the situation in the Gulf is the story of "Ardashīr and the Worm". The primary source for this story is the Kōrnāma which, we have seen, was originally compiled shortly after the events it describes.⁵⁰ A very similar version occurs in the better manuscripts of Firdausi's Shāh-Nāma.⁵¹ Yet, the story has been neglected by scholars as an historical source. It would appear that this is fundamentally due to the prominent role given by our sources to the mythical worm, which symbolizes Ahriman in his struggle against the Shāhanshāh, representing Ahura Mazdā. Indeed, many of the more derivative Shāh Nāma manuscripts elevate the importance of the heroic element to the extent of almost totally changing the historical background of the tale. In addition, although the story is briefly alluded to in Ṭabari,⁵² it lacks the historical sanction of a full scale inclusion in his history. However, the embroideries of later writers cannot obscure the fundamental appearance of the story in the early Pahlavi source, the Khvadhāynāma. Nor does it seem wise to dismiss a story which relates reputedly historical events with a mass of detail merely because that story is told within the framework of heroic convention. The reality of the episode to many early

Islamic sources is the mention of Kudjarān, the seat of the worm, by the geographers, and its location on the Persian Gulf borders of Fārs and Kirman.⁵³

Stripped of its heroic and mythical embellishments, the story is this. When Ardashīr came to power the coastal regions of southern Iran had slipped out of Parthian hands and were controlled by a local chieftan named Haftwad. Operating from a strong fortress at Kudjarān on the sea coast, he occupied the whole littoral of the "Sea of China" from Fārs to the borders of Sind, and possibly had some sort of alliance with the coastal tribes in Arabia. When Ardashīr first sent a force to subdue Haftwad, his army was ambushed at the foot of the citadel of Kudjarān and was forced to flee with a great loss of life and all the baggage. Following this defeat Ardashīr himself led a great expedition against Haftwad, who was reinforced by sea. A great battle was fought near Kudjarān, and although the result of the combat itself was indecisive, Haftwad's men were able to cut Ardashīr's communications and totally stop the supply of provisions to the royal camp. Hearing of Ardashīr's desperate position a pretender revolted in the hinterland of Fārs and plundered the royal palace at Ardashīr Kūra (Gūr). This compelled Ardashīr to retreat from the coast and re-establish his authority in Fārs. In retreat the army was harassed at every point by Haftwad's men who controlled the passes, and only the king and

a few others reached safety, perhaps by boat,⁵⁴ on his own territory. Later, having subdued the rebellion in Fars, Ardashīr launched yet another attack, the castle of Haftwad was taken by a ruse, and a fire temple or perhaps even a new town was founded there by the victor. Ardashīr himself returned to Ctesiphon, sending his troops under a subordinate to pacify Kirman.⁵⁵

The story makes excellent sense. Ardashīr, like later rulers of Fars, found it extremely hard to bring the unruly coastlands under control. Military campaigns in the coastal regions were restricted by the weather to three months in the spring, for in summer fodder was unobtainable, and in winter the roads were often impassible because of flash floods. Communications between the interior and the Gulf was hindered by the fact that there were few passes through the mountain ranges which run parallel to the coast, and in which armies were liable to ambush.⁵⁶ Haftwad, like the rulers of Kish and Hummuz after him, was particularly strong because he could control naval reinforcements.

The moral of the Haftwad episode was clear. The security of the littoral areas demanded total control of the Gulf, and Baṭn Ardashīr on the Arabian coast was not only a profitable entrepôt, but also a first step towards that control. By the 5th century, and probably much earlier, the Parthian outpost of Mazūn (the Oman) was brought under control.⁵⁷ The Sasanian presence as far

as the Oman was more than nominal. Dr. Wilkinson's recent research into the early Arab sources has led him to conclude that a large number of Persian settlers lived there during the Sasanian period, and that the entire qanat system is of Sasanian date.⁵⁸

Sasanian dominance of the Gulf, however, was by no means complete, for the peace was constantly troubled by incursions of Arabs from al-Bahrayn.⁵⁹ During the minority of Shāhpūr II (309-326)⁶⁰ they swarmed across the Gulf and plundered the country of southern Iraq,⁶¹ Khūzistān, and Fārs, including the city of Rēv Ardashīr.⁶² They carried off flocks and grain, and some even settled on the Persian coast. Shāhpūr viewed these attacks with such concern that his first military expedition which he led in person was directed against these raiders. Having annihilated the Arabs on the Persian shore,⁶³ he devastated the littoral of Bahrayn before pressing inland to Hajar and even as far as Yathrib (later re-named Medina) and possibly the borders of the Himyrite Kingdom of the Yemen.⁶⁴ During the campaign whole tribes were annihilated and wells were deliberately destroyed. Arabs who were made captive were tied together by cords piercing their shoulders, hence Shāhpūr's nickname, Dhū'l-Aktāf (Lord of the Shoulders).⁶⁵ Despite this savage expedition, the Gulf was not entirely free from Arab raiders. For, in the eleventh year of the reign of Hurmuzid IV (590 A.D.) we hear of fresh attacks on Fārs or the Sawād.⁶⁶

These continuing Arab attacks were, however, no more than a symptom of the great changes which occurred in eastern Arabia during the Sasanian period. It has been noted that the eastern coastline of Arabia has been rising since the relief of down-warping pressure with the formation of the rift zone. This continuing process has had radical effects within the last few thousand years, and the coastline has retreated in places up to 120 kilometres since the period of Ubaid settlements in the early fourth millennium B.C.. The tilting of strata, cutting off underground water flow from the western mountain rim of Arabia, in conjunction with the unexplained desiccation of the Arabian interior, has had disastrous effects on the economy of eastern Arabia.⁶⁷

Some of the more important of these changes seem to have occurred at the general period around the turn of the Christian era. Thus at Thāj, inland from Hafūf, a flourishing walled city of almost 40 hectares, with extensive suburbs, belonging to the South Arabian culture was totally abandoned during the floruit of Bibby's "Seleucid" pottery types. Although Thāj appears to have been beside a lake, the area is now open desert.⁶⁸

South of Qatīf extensive field systems lie ten to fifteen kilometres from the coast in what is now a waterless region over-run by dunes. Bibby was unable to estimate the total extent of

these fields because of the encroachment of dunes, but implies that the area exposed at the time of his research was in excess of 100 square kilometres. After excavating two eroded settlements he concluded that the fields had gone out of use early in the Christian era and suggested that this was the region of Gerrha.⁶⁹

About 30 kilometres to the south, by the village of ^cUqair, are the remains of a ruined city. Bibby, who examined the site in 1967, considered that the surface pottery was Islamic. To verify that the origins of the town were not earlier he sondaged beside a standing perimeter wall, but concluded that this too had Islamic footings, and that the settlement entirely dated from the Islamic period.⁷⁰ However, although I was not personally able to visit the site, I have been able to consult two collections of pottery from ^cUqair which are accessible in a western collection.⁷¹ These collections, one of which was made by a professional archaeologist and the other by an amateur, represent over 1,700 sherds from the site. Both collections seem to be preponderantly of Partho-Sasanian material. The larger collection distinguished between five areas of the site, and the study of it implies that Islamic pottery was concentrated in a single area, "the fort". This "fort", it is suggested, is the standing "town wall" excavated by Bibby and found to be Islamic, but it would seem to occupy only a portion of a much larger, earlier site. Thus, although any decisions on the area of the site or its date must await the

opportunity of a scientific examination, it does seem that there was at ^CUqair a major settlement of the Sasanian period which had decayed by the coming of Islam into a mere village. Any possible relation of ^CUqair with Gerrhae or with Batn Ardashir must remain in the balance.⁷² Similar evidence of abandoned settlement with broadly Partho-Sasanian pottery exists beyond the edges of the present Qatif oasis.⁷³

The Sasanian period then can be sketched as one of progressive and rapid desiccation of eastern Arabia. The tilting of Arabia reduced the underground flow to areas like Qatif, and at ^CUqair and Hufuf it stopped altogether. At the same time great areas of seabed were exposed which eroded away, choking vegetation already threatened by the reduced water supply. This must have led to a reduction in grazing land, subsequent overgrazing, and the creation of dustbowl conditions.⁷⁴

These conditions explain to a large extent the waves of Arab raiders who threw themselves upon the Persian coast all through the Sasanian period, and who emigrated in enormous numbers in the wake of the Muslim conquest. Our sources emphasize the poverty and misery so, clearly rather than being plunder hungry bedouin, the raiders should be looked upon as both nomads and agriculturalists driven to desperation by a diminishing food supply. Significantly, when Hummuzid IV payed off the raiders, he provided grain, flour, dates, and grapes, as well as silver.⁷⁵

More fundamentally, the impoverishment of eastern Arabia, the choking of the land routes by the formation of the great sand sea, and the navigational problems of Arabian waters⁷⁶ explain the shift of commercial interest in the Gulf area away from over-land routes across Arabia or towns like Gerrha and towards the richer, more developing Persian shore. From the point where Gerrha disappears from the map of Asia at the start of the Sasanian period till the last ten years with the boom in gold smuggling, the eastern shore of Arabia has been an area of reduced commercial significance beside the great entrepôts on the Gulf's northern shore.

The Sasanian period was one of remarkable prosperity for the lands bordering the northern shore of the Gulf. Besides the importance of Ctesiphon as the royal capital, agriculture boomed in Iraq and Khūzistān. Sasanian irrigation works in Iraq opened up enormous areas of fresh cultivation, as was demonstrated by Adams' archaeological survey in the Diyala region.⁷⁷ The largest irrigation project there was an extensive system of canals constructed to supply Shāhpūr I's new city of Buzurg-Shāhpūr,⁷⁸ and all over the plain Adams noted additions and extensions to the existing canal system. The most important new hydraulic project on the Iraqi plain was the construction of the great Nahrāwān Canal which took off from the Tigris below Takrit and watered its

eastern bank for almost 300 kilometres.⁷⁹ Elsewhere between the rivers, cultivation was carried on in what later became the great swamp.⁸⁰

Khūzistān was particularly developed under the Sasanians and became famous during this period for its sugar cane and rice production.⁸¹ We have noted Ardashīr's three foundations on the Shatt al-^cArab and his cities at Ram Hurmuz and Ahvaz. His successor restored Susa and Shustar besides constructing new cities at Gundishāpūr and Iran Shāpūr. Great new barrages, built with the help of Roman captives were thrown across the three main rivers, the Kar^cūn, the Diz and the Kārūn.⁸² Adams, in a recent archaeological survey⁸³ noted the extensive canal systems which flowed from these barrages, even cutting across natural divides. Supplementary irrigation was provided by the first extensive use of qanāts in the region. The largest settlement which Adams found in Khūzistān, the town of Gundishāpūr,⁸⁴ occupied almost 400 hectares, which must have represented a population at the lowest estimate, of about 50,000.⁸⁵ Iran Shāpūr was only slightly smaller, while other settlements existed on all the new canal systems. Indeed, Adams suggests that the total population of Upper Khūzistān was several times larger than it had ever been before and reached a level which has not been equaled since. An index of the great increase in wealth of Khūzistān was the level of late Sasanian tax returns, which was twelve times that of the Achaemenid period. The distribution of settlement in Khūzistān and elsewhere on the Gulf is illustrated on Fig. 4.

Fars, the homeland of the dynasty prospered as never before. Gūr, the great new circular city of Ardashīr, was built less than 120 kilometres from the Gulf coast and enclosed an area of 390 hectares, of which about a third was built up (mounded).⁸⁶ In view of the Sasanian hydraulic works in Khuzistān and Iraq, it is of interest to note that our sources relate a great drainage scheme connected with the foundation of Gūr.⁸⁷ The smaller circular city of Dārāb, which enclosed 227 hectares, was probably founded by a petty princeling during the Parthian period, but it was clearly of the greatest importance during the late Sasanian period.⁸⁸ At Istakhr Sasanian mounding included suburbs outside the city walls and probably covered about 90 hectares. At Bishāpūr, less than 100 kilometres from the Gulf on the banks of the Shāpūr River, a great new palace and city was built by Shāpūr II.⁸⁹ The area of the city was about 155 hectares and that of mounding, approximately 86.⁹⁰ The city's wealth was demonstrated by the spectacular finds, and especially the coins, from the excavations there. Indeed, the valley linking Bishāpūr and Gūr has many Sasanian mounds in it, in addition to the ruins of chahār tāqs and a remarkable hunting enclosure.⁹¹

In Kirmān province this period witnessed a determined colonization of the Karmania Deserta of Ptolemy,⁹² the great inland plains around Kirmān and Sīrjān, which are now the best land of the province. Ardashīr I or his son of the same name was responsible for the

foundation of Bih Ardashīr which is generally identified with Bardasīr or Guvāshīr of the mediaeval sources, the present day city of Kirmān, and the largest settlement on the Kirmān plain⁹³ (See Figs. 2 and 4). Sīrjān, the early Muslim capital of the province was almost certainly founded by Bahram IV (388-399) who was prince governor of Kirmān before he became King of Kings.⁹⁴ The same ruler may also have founded Kermānshāhan or Brahminābād on the Rafsanjān plain.⁹⁵

My own archaeological survey has confirmed the conclusions of Stein's, Caldwell's, and Lamberg-Karlovsky's surveys,⁹⁶ that these great plains, which depended entirely on qanāt irrigation were essentially unoccupied before the Sasanian period. Although archaeological sites of the Sasanian period are known from the Kirmān plain⁹⁷, and also from Sīrjān, no signs of earlier occupation have been found.

Despite the Sasanian activity on the upland plains and the establishment of Sīrjān as the capital of the province, the great development of the qanāt irrigated areas undoubtedly dates from no earlier than the 8th to 9th centuries A.D..⁹⁸ Until that period the settlements on the warm plain of Jīruft, closer to the Gulf were still the largest in the province.⁹⁹ In Jīruft a group of sites with a total area in the Sasanian period of almost 70

hectares dwarfed the Sirjān settlement, which did not exceed 30 hectares.¹⁰⁰ However, as these total settlement areas indicate, Kirman, despite its development, was still an underpopulated area besides Fārs and Khūzistan.

Nevertheless, the peace and prosperity of southern Iran should not be overestimated, for there was clearly a great deal of local insecurity. All the great Sasanian cities were strongly fortified. Gūr¹⁰¹ and Dārāb¹⁰² were surrounded by great moats and ramparts, while Istakhr¹⁰³ and Bishāpur¹⁰⁴ nestled behind a combination of walls and moats. On the coast, the town of Sirāf¹⁰⁵ was built with strong defences, while the architectural features of the Sasanian period at Tepe Yahyā suggested to the excavator a "citadel like structure".¹⁰⁶ Smaller Sasanian settlements from inland Kirman to the Persepolis plain stand out amongst other archaeological sites because of their preponderant "fortified" morphology. These sites rise sharply out of the surrounding plain, and are either remarkably high for their width or are dish-shaped, being higher at the edges than in the centre.¹⁰⁷ When tested by excavation such morphologies are almost always proved to result from the decay of large exterior defences.¹⁰⁸ It seems that in the Sasanian period, more than at almost any other period in the history of southern Iran, every little settlement found it necessary to protect itself against marauders.

One does not have to look far for the source of this insecurity. Even before facing the worm at Kujarān, Ardashīr found it necessary to establish his power over the "Kurds", the nomad tribes and the high mountain dwellers of South Persia.¹⁰⁹ The rulers of the most powerful of these groups, the Balūchān (of South Kirmān) and the Marīnjān (of eastern Fārs) are counted by the author of Eranshāhr, among the seven mountain rulers of Iran, while a Nestorian bishop was appointed specifically to care for the souls of those in the "Kurdish encampments".¹¹⁰ Smaller groups included the Qufs in Firdausī's "Kush skilled in the use of the dagger." This group, together with the Balūch, devastated a whole district "where they killed and pillaged ravaged and upturned" during the reign of Khusrau Anurshivān. Khusrau's consequent campaign of annihilation seems to have provided a brief period of peace for the plain dwellers, but by the Arab conquest these groups were again a problem.¹¹¹

On the Gulf itself, the Seleucid and Parthian settlements at Hurmuzea and Hieratus on the Persian coast and Bahrain Island and Gerrha on the Arabian were noted in the last Chapter, as were the larger settlements at the head of the Gulf in the region of Mesene. We have seen that this was a period of declining prosperity on the Arabian coast. Nevertheless, there was probably a major settlement inland at Hajar (Hufūf) which was the seat of the Persian Marzubān¹¹² and at the coastal town of Bitn Ardashīr

(^CUqair). The seats of Nestorian bishops (Fig. 3) give some idea of other centres of settlement. Besides sees at Hajar, Bitn Ardashīr, and Mazūn, there was a bishop of Abdai (or Darai or Deirin) which scholars have alternately identified with Tarut Island off Qatif, or the Island of Bahrain,¹¹³ where the major Seleucid site¹¹⁴ was abandoned by this period. Other sees were at Mesmahig and Todouru which are unidentified, but were clearly in the same area, and by 676 a Metropolitan was established at Beit Quatraya (Qatar).¹¹⁵

On the Persian coast the old town of Hurmuz, which was probably the Omana of the Periplus increased in size during the Sasanian period. One rather late source mentions it as a foundation Ardashīr,¹¹⁶ but this probably a confusion with Ram Hurmuzd Ardashīr in Khuzistan. Nevertheless, there was a Nestorian bishop,¹¹⁷ and settlement in the Mīnāb River delta expanded from a little over 20 hectares in the Achaemeno-Seleucid period (Yaḥyā II) to between 50 and 60 hectares in the Sasanian period.¹¹⁸ Out-lying settlements were established under the Sasanians on Hurmuz Island¹¹⁹ and also on the Musandam Peninsula.¹²⁰

There was virtually no Sasanian settlement on the coast for 250 kilometres west of Hurmuz. However, from a point to the west of the modern town of Bandar Lengeh, a string of small

Partho-Sasanian settlements (the largest is 25 hectares) hug the coastline and total 74 hectares in area. Although relatively small, these sites are of the greatest importance and will be returned to in Chapter . They are situated on the most desolate part of the whole Persian coast, where wells are very few and water is almost entirely obtained from covered cisterns which collect run off. Even today there is virtually no agriculture in the area, and the population is extremely small. Nevertheless, the raison d'etre of the Partho-Sasanian sites is clear, for large oyster middens, up to 600 metres long and associated with Partho-Sasanian pottery litter the beaches. Undoubtedly the inhabitants of these settlements were engaged in pearling on the banks nearby, but their scale of operations was very much greater than when Nearchus visited their predecessors.

Indeed, the indications from these settlements are that pearling there was of greater importance during the Sasanian than at any earlier or subsequent period. Moreover, it was a most profitable undertaking, for fine pottery on these sites included imports from India (Fig. 9), Balūchistān (Fig. 8), and Mesopotamia.¹²¹

Thus, at least from the evidence on the Persian shore,¹²² the origin of large scale pearling can be firmly placed in the late Parthian and very early Sasanian period. This is of great importance since pearling, as will be seen below, was the major

export industry of the Gulf during subsequent periods. It will be suggested that the growth in pearling during the late Parthian and early Sasanian periods played a crucial role in the capital formation which encouraged the growth of large scale commerce from Rēv Ardashīr, the predecessor of the great Islamic ports.¹²³

Beyond the pearling sites a large settlement existed by the end of the Sasanian period at Sīrāf, 40 kilometres to the west of Narband Bay, on a stretch of coast scarcely noted by Nearchus. Sīrāf, the later history of which is one of the central points of this study, was built in a narrow bay where the mountains in places approach to within a kilometre of the coast. This situation did, however, have considerable natural advantages. Being less than a day's journey from the rich agricultural valleys of both Jam and Gāllēdār, it was better supplied with foodstuffs than any site on the Persian coast between Hurmuz and Būshahr. Moreover, it stood at the end of the only pass through the mountain ranges which was feasible for camels.¹²⁴ This route led straight to Gūr, and it was as a port and defensive bastion of Ardashīr's capital that Sīrāf probably first came into prominence. One of the earliest buildings on the site was a fort, probably about 62 metres square. Dr. Whitehouse has indicated its "family likeness" to Roman works on the frontier in Iraq, notably the defences of Singara. He suggests the possibility that the fort was built for Shāhpūr II by some of the Roman legionaires who were captured at Singara in 360, and who

we know were employed on public works in Fārs. In this case the fort might well have served to stiffen the coastal defences against the threat of renewed Arab raids such as occurred in Shāhpūr's minority.¹²⁵

Almost one and a quarter kilometres from the fortress a triangular bastion of the city wall, 11 metres wide and associated with three Sasanian coins, was excavated. Elsewhere, at Sīraf, Sasanian coins were found in the lower levels of excavations in the Islamic residential area (Site F), though apparently no Sasanian material was found in the sondage at Site A, less than 200 metres from the fortress. Surface finds confirm the Sasanian background of the site and a Byzantine solidus of immediately post-Sasanian date (651-659) was excavated in higher levels.¹²⁶ The distribution of finds imply that by the end of the Sasanian period Sīraf was a fortified settlement of some wealth, occupying an area of perhaps 100 hectares, though not all that area was built up.¹²⁷ Subsidiary settlements were found on the route leading inland and also on the coast nearby,¹²⁸ and included a kiln site producing pottery types similar to those found in the Sasanian levels at Tepe Yahya.¹²⁹

Sīraf was not, however, the largest site on the coast of Fārs. The Būshahr Peninsula, which had been the location of Hieratus, the only settlement on the Gulf which Nearchus had distinguished as polis, had flourished beyond these promising beginnings.

Indeed, a scatter of Partho-Sassanian pottery covers much of the peninsula. In many areas no doubt this scatter does not represent settlement, but simply fields.¹³⁰ Nevertheless, the area of mounding (indicating the position of actual habitation) exceeds 450 hectares.¹³¹ A remarkably wide range of Sasanian and Parthian pottery types were found on the surface. Although there is very little evidence that pottery was imported from inland Fārs, imports from along the Gulf included a large number of Mesopotamian types, some from Balūghistān, including the find, black painted orange ware illustrated in Fig. 7 A-C, and the superb red polished ware (Fig. 7D-F), which had undoubtedly been brought from India at some time between 0 and 300 A.D.. The most remarkable feature, however, was the wide surface distribution of the bifurcated-rim bowl (illustrated in Appendix I) which probably dates from the period c. 500-750 A.D.. The frequency with which this type appears over almost the entire surface area indicates that at this one period almost 450 hectares were inhabited. This represents a very considerable settlement by any standards, and is probably the largest archaeological site of any period on the Gulf, with the exception of Abbāsīd Basra.¹³² It is of particular interest that the settlement at Būshāhr was larger than any of the well known trading cities of the Islamic period.

It is necessary, because of the size and importance of this site, to examine it in some detail. The Būshāhr Peninsula is an "island" formed of calcareous beach rock, 21 kilometres long and up

to 6 kilometres wide, jutting into the sea and separated from the mainland by easily floodable sabkha,¹³³ 15 kilometres across at the narrowest point. The only perennial water sources on the peninsula are wells, most of which are brackish. Agriculture must always have depended on laborious irrigation from them,¹³⁴ and the water demands of the great Sasanian city could only be met through the construction of dams to conserve the seasonal run off from the wadis. Thus, although it is unlikely that the peninsula itself could ever have supported a large population, there was probably always ample food resources less than two days away by donkey. For the coastal plain opposite Būshahr is broad and relatively rich, with the delta of the Shāphūr River, the first perennial sweet water west of the Mīnāb, just to the north of the peninsula.

The broad band of sabkha must have prevented communications with the mainland during wet weather or after exceptional tides, unless as today, there was a causeway across, and there is no surviving evidence that this was so. Once on dry land, it was only a three day journey up the precipitous gorge of the Rūd-i Shāhpūr to Bīshāpūr, the royal city of Shahpur.¹³⁵ An easier route to the interior, passable by camels, entered the mountains at Ahrām, and led to Farāshband, on the plain linking Bīshāpūr with Gūr.¹³⁶

The Sasanian settlement was concentrated on the coast of the peninsula facing the open sea. Its function as a port is indicated by the location of the two largest groups of mounds, one on the west coast near the modern village of Rīshahr, and the second at the southern tip of the peninsula, around the modern village of Haliyla. These concentrations of settlement face the two sheltered anchorages the peninsula provides.¹³⁷ The larger group of mounds is at Rīshahr, where the deepest deposits (over six metres in the eroding beach section) surround the ruins of an imposing fort. This fortification, which faces the sea, is roughly rectangular, having sides of 300 and 390 metres. It is surrounded by a ditch 28 to 30 metres wide, cut at least three and a half metres through bedrock. Its eroded mudbrick walls survive as mounding which still rises up to 12 metres above the moat. Some scholars have identified the fort as Portuguese,¹³⁸ and one has suggested that it was built by the Dutch.¹³⁹ Certainly it was reused in post-mediaeval times, most recently by the Qājār troops in 1857.¹⁴⁰ However, its position in the midst of a substantial Sasanian site, the lack of Islamic pottery underlying it in the beach section, and the surface pottery all suggest that the fort itself was pre-Islamic.

Below the fort and extending in a ruinous state for more than 100 metres out to sea are the remains of a jetty almost 5 metres wide and faced on either side with marine boulders. Fortunately, here again there is a clue to its date; as the beach shows, the

jetty is overlain at the landward end by buildings, the floors of which are covered with the same distinctive late Sasanian pottery which is found elsewhere on the site.

No trace of either a fort or jetty survives by the southern mounds, but here a creek, now silted, probably served as an inner harbour. This creek, which connects through the narrow tip of the peninsula between the open sea and tidal channels in the sabkha, could quite easily have been mistaken for a channel between a river and the sea. It is, I suggest, "the channel running from the river to the sea called Heratemis" where Nearchus anchored his ships.¹⁴¹ It is lined with mounding.

Between the two harbours lies a string of smaller mounds (Fig. 6). Many appear to consist of clusters or individual buildings perched on rocky slopes above the shore, taking full advantage of the sea breezes which make the hot summer tolerable at Būshahr. Since many of these mounds rest on the bare rock, some of the construction of the buildings could be seen. They were generally built of partially dressed stones, mortared with earth, and often floored and plastered with gypsum. Although some buildings seemed to be up to 30 metres square, most were quite small, often less than 10 metres square. ~~Yet~~ an indication of their wealth was that several had private wells, which on the more elevated ridges must have been sunk almost one hundred metres to reach the water table. These were,

no doubt, the houses or the summer pavilions of the richer inhabitants of the ports.

One group of buildings, the plan of which could not be determined on the ground, was built of ashlar with gypsum mortar throughout. The use of ashlar has no parallel in recent building practice, and there are no other examples from post-Achaemenid archaeological sites on the Persian side of the Gulf.¹⁴² On the south of the Gulf, ashlar construction was used on the Seleucid temple at Falaika, and on some of the "Seleucid" graves and other structures on Bahrain.¹⁴³ However, it is not necessary to assume that these buildings, which have surface pottery continuing as late as the 5th to 8th centuries A.D., were originally Hellenistic, for ashlar construction appears in the major Sasanian buildings at Bīshāpūr, and in the platform of the fire temple at Cūr.¹⁴⁴ One might surmise that these buildings at Būshahr were of similar importance.

To the east of the coastal ridge of the peninsula, a lower eroded area with frequent remains of walls and occasionally irrigation channels must have marked the principal area of agriculture. Small mounds indicated farmsteads or rich suburban homes. The north of the peninsula, as can be seen on Fig. 6, was almost devoid of settlement, unless there was occupation on the northern tip, which is presently occupied by the town of Būshahr.

On the eastern edge of the highest part of the peninsula were the only signs of defensive works apart from the central citadel at Rishahr. A fort of less than 150 metres square and four isolated watch towers all faced inland. For its seaward defence the city must have depended on Sasanian naval power.

This city was clearly a maritime centre of great importance. The agricultural resources of the peninsula by themselves could never have been sufficient to support more than a fraction of the population. The location of the peninsula, jutting into the Gulf, the position of the major settlements facing natural anchorages, and the presence of the jetty all testify to Būshahr's dependance on the sea. The range of its maritime contacts is illustrated by the pottery types from as far as India to the east and Mesopotamia to the west. However, the factors which brought about the prosperity of Būshahr were fragile, for the inhabited area of about 450 hectares in the 7th century (representing a city of at least 50,000 inhabitants¹⁴⁵) had fallen by the 9th century to the limit of the agricultural support from the peninsula itself, about 20 hectares.

Such a major settlement, with such a spectacular history, must surely have left its mark on the historical record, and the information from historical sources might be expected to help explain the factors which created and then removed its prosperity.

The very name Būshahr is suggestive of a foundation of Ardashīr. Lockhart and others have suggested that it represents Bukht Ardashīr.¹⁴⁶ This was a town built by Ardashīr on the sea coast of Fārs, but its subsequent history is obscure.¹⁴⁷ An alternative identification suggests itself in the name of the village Rīshahr which stands on the largest area of Sasanian mounding. Several scholars, without knowing of the archaeological remains there, have suggested that Rīshahr represents Rēv Ardashīr, another foundation of Ardashīr,¹⁴⁸ although the Elamite scholar Hūsing considered that it embodied an Elamite word, rishair, meaning "great", an epithet frequently used of the goddess Kiririsha who was worshipped in the Elamite temple at Liyan, on the edge of the later mounding.¹⁴⁹ However, the location of Rēv Ardashīr has been disputed between two possible sites.

To resolve the identification of Rēv Ardashīr it is necessary to consider the historical information on the Sasanian city. Rēv Ardashīr is described by both Ṭabarī and Ṭamza as a foundation of Ardashīr near the coast of Fārs.¹⁵⁰ The city was plundered by Arab raiders from across the Gulf during the minority of Shāphūr II, but seems to have quickly recovered.¹⁵¹ For its importance from the 5th century onwards is documented by its position as the seat of the Nestorian Metropolitan of all Fārs, who apart from having authority over the Nestorian bishops of the inland cities, had by the 7th century, a maritime jurisdiction including all India, and stretching as far as Qal'ah in Malaya.¹⁵² Rīshahr is mentioned

in the abbreviated version of the Geography attributed to Moses of Chorene (probably containing information of the 5th to 7th centuries A.D.) under the name of Rīshahr-i Pahrsan (Rīshahr the watch post or customs post) as the source of excellent pearls.¹⁵³ In addition, Yāqūt, in a curious note, remarks that under the Sasanians it was inhabited by the Kushta Daftarān who write in a script called Hasiq about medicine, astrology, and the cabbalistic sciences.¹⁵⁴ During the Arab conquest a bloody battle, compared by Balādhurī to that of Gādisiyyam, was fought near Rīshahr and opened up the interior of Fārs to the Arab armies.¹⁵⁵ Sasanian coins with the mint marks have been attributed to Rīshahr by modern scholars.¹⁵⁶

The identification of Rēv Ardashīr at later periods has been fraught with difficulties. Ḥamza notes that Sasanian Rēv Ardashīr was at his time called Rīshahr.¹⁵⁷ There is only one Rīshahr in the contemporary sources and that was clearly near Arrajān. Iṣṭakhrī and Maqdisī describe Rīshahr as a rural canton in the region of Arrajān, situated on the River Ṭab.¹⁵⁸ According to Maqdisī, it was a day distant from Arrajān City in the direction of Mahrubān on the border of Khūzistān.¹⁵⁹ Later sources such as Ibn al-Balkhī and Ḥamd Allāh Gazvīnī describe Rīshahr as a town on the sea shore in the district of Arrajān near the border of Khūzistān.¹⁶⁰ The first indisputable reference to Rīshahr on the Būshahr peninsula occurs in the itinerary of the Sinhalese envoys to Egypt at the end of the 13th century, although subsequent references

are common.¹⁶¹ For this reason Noeldeke and Marquart concluded that Sasanian Rēv Ardashīr was to be found in the area of Arrajān.¹⁶²

However, there is a line of contrary evidence. Balādhurī, writing almost a century before the geographical sources, describes in his highly considered work on the Arab conquests a battle which took place near Rīshahr which he locates in the district of Tawaj of the Kūra of Shāhpūr in Fārs. The Persian army was commanded in person by Shāhrek, the Marzubān of Fārs, and after his defeat of the city fell to the Muslim forces. Tabarī, who follows a very different group of sources for his account of the conquest of Fārs, describes the battle of Tawaj in a context and with circumstantial details which clearly imply that this was Balādhurī's battle of Rīshahr.¹⁶³

Both accounts indicate that Rīshahr-Rēv Ardashīr was near Tawaj, which can be clearly located on the Shāhpūr River, north-east of Būshahr and over 160 kilometres from Rīshahr of Arrajān. This Rīshahr could never have been in the district of Tawaj, though the Rīshahr on the Būshahr Peninsula, the natural harbour for the settlement at Tawaj, might well have been in its district.¹⁶⁴

Schwarz¹⁶⁵ suggested that Balādhurī was confused in his account of the battle of Rīshahr, describing it as near Tawaj simply because that was the base of the Sasanian armies. However, the confirmatory evidence we have noted in Tabarī clearly suggests that the battle was not fought near Arrajān, and most recent scholars

have accepted the evidence for two early Islamic Rīshahrs. However, opinion has been sharply divided over which of these two was the great Sasanian city. Christensen, Piguleschova, and Göbl¹⁶⁶, for example, consider it was near Arrajān, and Hasan, Streck, and Lockhart¹⁶⁷ locate it near Būshahr.

Archaeological research adds a new dimension to this controversy. I have not personally examined the area of Rīshahr of Arrajān, but Dr. Hansman, who searched for a Sasanian city there, informs me that there are no Sasanian sites of any size (say above 30-40 hectares) in the area. This is in strong contrast to the large mounds of Sasanian date around Rīshahr on the Būshahr Peninsula. The conclusion is almost inescapable that Balādhurī's identification must be preferred, and that the mounding around Rīshahr can be clearly identified with the important maritime city of Rēv Ardashīr which the Marzubān himself was prepared to protect with his life. Rēv Ardashīr was not only the largest settlement on the Gulf during the Sasanian period, but as will be seen, it played an important role in Sasanian maritime activities in the Indian Ocean.

SUMMARY OF FINAL PORTION OF CHAPTER 5

Sasanian Activity in the Indian Ocean

Rēv Ardashīr was the seat of the Nestorian Metropolitan of Fārs, who by the 7th century was engaged in missionary activities in India and as far away as Malaya. Several Nestorian monks from the Gulf had previously travelled to India as merchants, while other Nestorian records refer to maritime trade with India and China.

The Sasanian government too was active beyond the Gulf. By the fifth century the Sasanians controlled the Indus valley, and with it merchantile centres which controlled important exports, and already traded as far as Malaya. By the 6th century diplomatic relations were established with the rulers of the Deccan, and if we are to believe Tabarī and other historians, a maritime expedition was even mounted against Ceylon. In the later half of the same century Yemen was conquered from the sea and was subsequently ruled by Persian governors. Gulf traders were the spear head of the aggressive Sasanian policy. They were common in South India in the 4th century, and by the 6th were trading in the ports of Ethiopia and totally controlled the export of silks from Ceylon, despite every effort of the Byzantines to break their hold. Greek, Ethiopian, and even South Yemenite merchantile

merchandise activity decayed during this period, and the
Sasanians, the Gulf merchants emerged, together with Indians,
as the dominant merchandise power in the western Indian Ocean.

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- Yahya=Lamberg-Karlovsky, C. C., Excavations at Tepe Yahya, Iran, 1967-69: Progress Report I, Bulletin of the American School of Prehistoric Research 27, Cambridge, Mass. 1970.
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Fig. 1. The western Indian Ocean showing some of the sites mentioned in Chapters 3 and 4. The area enclosed in dotted lines is shown on Figs. 2, 3, 4. (Joint production with D. Whitehouse)

Fig. 2. The Gulf showing cities founded by Ardashir and major Sasanian sites. Names which are underlined refer to towns the positions of which are uncertain and are discussed in the text.

Fig. 2. The Gulf showing cities founded by Ardashir and major Sasanian sites. Names which are underlined refer to towns the positions of which are uncertain and are discussed in the text.

Fig. 3. Nestorian dioceses in the Gulf showing the seats of bishops mentioned in the synod lists published by [redacted] bot. The diocese of Hurmuzea which [redacted] not recorded on the lists is also shown.

Fig. 3. Nestorian dioceses in the Gulf showing the seats of bishops mentioned in the synod lists published by Chabot. The diocese of Hurmuzza which is not recorded on the lists is also shown.

NOTES

¹The death of Yazdgard III is given by Göbl, taf. 13 as 649 (Sasanian reign dates are hereafter given on Göbl's authority.). Chris suggests 651 or 652 (p. 508). Perhaps a more significant date is the capture of Ctesiphon in 637 or the battle of Nihāvand in 642.

²See especially the work of Constantine VII Porphyrogenitus, Romilly Jenkins, Byzantium: The Imperial Centuries A.D. 610 to 1071, London 1966, pp. 258-259.

³Sasanian inscriptions are listed in Chris pp. 50-53 and Pigul, pp. 93-97. See especially E. Herzfeld, Paikuli, Monument and Inscriptions of the Early History of the Sasanian Empire, Berlin 1924; and W. B. Henning, "The Great Inscription of Šāpūr I", B.S.O.A.S. 9, 1939, pp. 823-849.

⁴The Avesta is ed. by J. Darmesteter, Le Zend Avesta, Annales du Musée Guimet, 21, 22, and 24, 1892-93. Chris pp. 56-58 discusses the religious literature.

⁵The edition used was Kārnamā. It is discussed in Chris, p. 58; Pigul pp. 98-100.

⁶Marquart, Catalogue, for date see p. 5; Pigul, pp. 97-98.

⁷Both versions are published in Marquart, Ērānshahr with notes. Pp. III-VII discuss the two versions. Text and trans. of the abbreviated version are found in J. de St. Martin (who thought it was apocryphal), Memoires historiques et géographiques sur l'Arménie, Paris 1819. The longer version is ed. and trans. by Le. P. Arsene Soukry, Géographie de Moïse de Corène, Venice 1881.

⁸The Latin and Greek historical sources are discussed in Chris, pp. 74-76.

⁹Two versions of the text are edited and analyzed by J. D. M. Derrett, "The history of Palladius of the races of India and the Brahmans", Classica and Mediaevalia 21, 1961, pp. 64-135, text on pp. 97-99 and 108-135, also "The Theban Scholasticus and Malabar in c. 355-60", J.A.O.S. 82, 1962, pp. 21-31. He discusses the date and concludes, p. 26, that the journey was in about 355-60.

¹⁰E. O. Winstedt, The Christian Topography of Cosmas Indicopluestes, Cambridge 1909, p. 11, quoted by Derrett, "The Theban. . .", p. 23.

¹¹The text was made available by G. Coedès, Textes d'auteurs grecs et latins relatifs à l'Extrême-Orient depuis le 4^e siècle av. J.C. jusqu'au 14^e siècle, Paris 1910, pp. 98-102 from C. Müller's edition of Pseudo-Callisthenes, Life of Alexander (called by J. D. M. Derrett, "The Theban Scholasticus and Malabar in c. 355-60", J.A.O.S. 82, 1962, pp. 21-31, "the worst of them [mss] and the poorest in readings") and De Brachmanibus by St. Ambrose. Scholars such as Tibbetts, "Pre-Islamic Arabia", p. 203; Warmington, p. 120, used this edition. See also Miller, pp. 190-191.

¹²Derrett, op. cit. in note 9.

¹³McCrintle, Cosmas, p. xiv quoted.

¹⁴Ibid., p. xxvii quoted.

¹⁵Cosmas, McCrintle, pp. 39 inter alia., discussed in McCrintle, Introduction to Cosmas, pp. iv-x.

¹⁶Chabot

¹⁷e.g. the letter by Timothy I (Patriarch from 780-823) to Mar Sergius, Metropolitan of Elam, quoted below, p.

¹⁸Colless, p. 19. Pigul, pp. 116-118, discusses the hagiographical sources.

¹⁹See below, p. 00

²⁰Translated in S. Beal, Buddhist Records of the Western World, London 1906 (2nd edition).

²¹The Muslim historians are discussed below, in Chapter 7. See Dunlop pp. 70-71 for their methods and Chris, pp. 59-74 for their sources on the Sasanian material.

²²Chris, pp. 59-74; Dunlop, pp. 46-47; 173-174.

²³Mas'ūdī, Tanbīh, B.C.A. VIII, trans, de Carra de Vaux, pp. 150 ff; Chris, pp. 66-67.

²⁴Chris, p. 261. A few Pahlavi sources are preserved in translations. The most important is the so-called Letter of Tansar which survives in a Persian abbreviation of an Arabic translation, Pigul, pp. 100-102.

²⁵Chris, p. 60 discusses Firdausī's source. Ḥamza, p. 21, trans. p. 14, discusses the translations available.

²⁶The Sasanian settlement at Sirāf is discussed below, p. .
I am grateful to Dr. Whitehouse for his views on the pottery.

²⁷A bibliography of excavations in Iraq which have produced Partho-Sasanian material is provided by R. V. Ricciardi, "Sasanian Pottery from Tell Mahuz", Mesopotamia 5-6, 1970-1971, pp. 428-429 and footnote.

²⁸The pottery from the first season is published by R. V. Ricciardi, "Pottery from Choche", Mesopotamia II, 1967, pp. 93-104. In Mesopotamia 5-6, p. 471, she describes a 6th century hoard above the excavations.

²⁹R. V. Ricciardi, "Sasanian Pottery from Tell Mahuz", Mesopotamia 5-6, 1970-1971, pp. 427-482. Note especially graves containing coins, p. 430.

³⁰Yahya, p. 5 for excavator's date; carbon dates, pp. 22, 131; inscribed sherd, p. 132 (by Prof. R. Frye); seal, p. 8. I am grateful to Prof. Lamberg-Karlovsky for discussing the pottery with me and allowing me to use his material.

³¹Personal communication.

³²Dr. Ricciardi informs me of its discovery on the surface near to Ctesiphon and assures me she has not seen the type in any of the unpublished collections she has examined.

³³Red Polished Ware is exceptionally fine, with a fabric reminiscent of Arretine, but with forms which are in no way comparable. It is described more fully in David Whitehouse and Andrew Williamson, "Sasanian Maritime Trade", Iran XI, 1973, pp. 38-39.

³⁴Naqsh-i Rostam in Persepolis III. The other sites, personal communication.

³⁵Archaeological survey 1968.

³⁶Archaeological survey 1970.

³⁷A type which might represent the early Sasanian horizon is one of burnished bowls with sharply pointed rims intermediate between Hellenistic "beaks" found at Pasargadae and the later burnished bowls.

³⁹J. Hansman, "The Problems of Qūmis", J.R.A.S. 1968.

⁴⁰Ardashīr's Gūr and Shāhpūr I's Bishāpūr both contained royal residences. For their positions, see below, p.

⁴¹Chris pp. 46-47.

⁴²Chris pp. 85-86 describes the fragmentation of southern Iran at the start of the 3rd century. Ibid, pp. 86-90 on Ardashīr's conquests.

⁴³The cities founded by Ardashīr are listed in Ḥamza, text, pp. 46-49, trans. pp. 33-34; Tabarī, pp. 819-820, Noeldeke, pp. 19-20; Tha alibi, pp. 485-486; Firdausī V, pp. 295, 303, 385-387; Nihāyutu'l arab, pp. 218 ff..

⁴⁴Le Strange, pp 233, 237.

⁴⁵For these see John Hansman, "Charax and the Karkheh", Iranica Antiqua VII, 1967, pp. 21-58.

⁴⁶Rēv Ardashīr is discussed below, p.39; Bokht Ardashīr is discussed below, pp. 15-16; Kujarān Ardashīr is discussed below in Chapter 7.

⁴⁷Ḥamza, p. 48. Tabarī I, p. 820, Noeldeke, p. 20.

⁴⁸Gerrha disappears from history at this period.

⁴⁹Noeldeke, p. 18.

⁵⁰Kārnāma, Sects. VI-VIII, trans., pp. 24-38. The Kārnāma is discussed above, p. 4.

⁵¹Firdausī V, pp. 308-330. Moule's edition of the Shāh Nāma relates best to the account given in the Kārnāma, and elsewhere with the accounts in Tabarī, et. al. derived from the common source of the Khvadhāynāma. A greatly elaborated version is given by R. Levy, trans. from Beroukhin's Teheran, 1934 edition (The Epic of the Kings, London 1967).

⁵²Tabarī, trans. Noeldeke, p. 19 +10.

⁵³The evidence for the location of Kujarān (spelled this way in Firdausī V, p. 308), is discussed in Chapter 7 below. Variant spellings are Gūzārān (Kārnāma, p. 24) and Kōchārān, Noeldeke, p. 19. The fortress was probably in the village of Alar, (Noeldeke, p. 19,) or Gular (Kārnāma, p. 24). See also V. Minorski in EI₂.

⁵⁴Kārnāma, p. 30 says by boat; Firdausī V, p. 318 implies by land.

⁵⁵The attack on Kirman is not mentioned in Sanjana's edition of Kārnāma, but is included in Antia's edition, see Marquart, Catalogue, p. 78, and Firdausī V, p. 330.

⁵⁶Ibn al-Balkhī, "Description of the Province of Fārs", trans., G. Le Strange, J.R.A.S. 1912, p. 329 has a useful section on the difficulty of campaigning in the coastlands.

⁵⁷Marquart, Ērānshahr, p. 43.

⁵⁸J. C. Wilkinson, "Arab-Persian Relations in Sasanid Oman", paper read at the Seminar for Arabian Studies, London, September 1972.

⁵⁹The raids are described in Ṭabarī, pp. 836-839, Noeldeke, pp. 53-56; Tha^calibī, pp. 616-619; Ḥamza, text pp. 51-52, trans. pp. 37-38; Nihāyutu'l arab pp. 229-230; Mas ūdī, Murūj, II, pp. 175-181.

⁶¹The Sawād. On the meaning of this see Le Strange, p. 24, especially note 1.

⁶²Ṭabarī, p. 836, Noeldeke, p. 54, Rishāhr, Ardashīr Kūra, and Fārs.

⁶³Tha^calibī, p. 518 mentions that Shāhpūr drove the Arabs from the Sawād. The Zend Avesta implies the Sawād also (Darmesteter, Annales du Musée Guimet II, pp. 401-402) noting that the Arabs held the region of the river Ūlay through the eruption of horsemen, but see note 62.

⁶⁴Firdausī V, p. 429 maintains that Shāhpūr reached the Yemen.

⁶⁵Ḥamza, p. 52;

⁶⁶Ṭabarī, Noeldeke, p. 270 describes an attack on the Sawād. Nihāyutu'l arab p. 233 mentions Fārs.

⁶⁷Discussed in Chapter 3.

⁶⁸Bibby, pp. 316, 322, 323, 327, 367-368, map on p. 369.

⁶⁹Ibid, pp. 318, 327, 328, 372-373.

⁷⁰Ibid., pp. 318, 319, 323-325, 372.

⁷¹Peabody Museum, Harvard University accession numbers 55/26/60, 12047-12084 collected by E. Field in 1955; Accession numbers 59/26/60, 12610-12648 collected by G. Naranjian in 1956-1958, the larger collection. I am grateful to Prof. C. C. Lamberg-Karlovsky, Curator of Near Eastern Archaeology at the Peabody for access to these valuable collections.

⁷²The identification of Gerra with ^CUqair rests first on the linguistic relationship of the two words, and second on ^CUqair's position at the end of the natural trail from Hufūf (Atenae?) to the Gulf. See Bibby, p. 318.

⁷³Bibby, p. 313.

⁷⁴See Bibby, p. 374.

⁷⁵

⁷⁶See above, Chapter 3.

⁷⁷R. Mc. Adams, Land Behind Baghdad, Chicago 1965, pp. 69-83. Several of Adams' diagnostic "Sasanian" types have a much longer time span than just the Sasanian period (See Appendix I), but his distributions would still seem to broadly reflect Sasanian settlement.

⁷⁸Ibid., p. 70, describes Buzurg Shāhpūr. It was a totally new city of about 150 hectares.

⁷⁹The best description of the canal, with map, is in G. Le Strange, "Description of Mesopotamia and Baghdad written about the year 900 A.D. by Ibn Serapion", J.R.A.S. 1895, pp. 265-277. Le Strange, pp. 57-61.

⁸⁰Le Strange, pp. 26-27.

⁸¹Marquart, Catalogue, p. 72 and references.

⁸²See especially Hamza, p. 48 for Ardashīr's canal building activity.

⁸³Robert Mc. C. Adams, "Agriculture and Urban Life in Early Southwestern Iran", Science 136 (3511) pp. 109-122.

⁸⁴For excavations at Jundishāpūr see, Robert Mc.C. Adams and Donald P. Hansen, "Archaeological Reconnaissance and Soundings at Jundi Shapur", Ars Orientalis 7, 1968, pp. 53-70; "Soundings at Gunde Shapur", The Memorial Volume of the Vth International Congress of Iranian Art and Archaeology, Teheran 1972, I, pp. 300-302.

⁸⁵The evidence for estimating the population of archaeological sites is discussed in Chapter 2.

⁸⁶Stein, "Persis", pp. 114-122 and plan 1; Schmidt, pl. 18-19.

⁸⁷Le Strange, p. 206 summarizes the evidence.

⁸⁸ Stein, "Persis", pp. 190-194, plan 10; Marquart, Catalogue, sect. 42 and pp. 93-94.; Schwartz, P., Iran im Mittelalter nach den arabischen Geographen, Leipzig, 1896-1936, p. 105.

⁸⁹ Survey 1969 for area of Sasanian mounding. E. Schmidt, The Treasury of Persepolis, Chicago 1935, pp. 107-109; Schmidt, Flights, p. 12 and pl. 8 and 9.

⁹⁰ R. Girshman, Fouilles de Châpour I, Musée du Louvre Department des Antiquités orientales, Serie Archaeologique, 1971, p. 33 for the area of the city. Survey 1969 for the area of Sasanian mounding. R. Girshman, Fouilles de Châpour II Musée du Louvre Department des Antiquités orientales, Serie Archaeologique, 1956, Les mosaics. Schmidt, pl. 23 and 22.

⁹¹ Survey 1969. The "hunting enclosure" appears on air photos.

⁹² Ptolemy 6,6; 6,8.

⁹³ Marquart, Erānshahr, para. 40; Hamza, p. 46, trans. p. 33. For the identification see Marquart in Erānshahr, pp. 90-91; Le Strange, p. 303.

⁹⁴ Marquart, Erānshahr, para. 39; Marquart in Erānshahr, p. 90.

⁹⁵ Marquart in Erānshahr, p. 90

⁹⁶ Stein, Recon.; J. R. Caldwell, Investigations at Tal-i-Iblis, Illinois State Museum Reports no. 9, Springfield, Illinois, 1967.

⁹⁷ e.g. cairns at Sar-i Asiab, excavated by Lamberg-Karlovsky in 1967, personal communication. Survey 1969, sites T6 and T 12.

⁹⁸ This development is discussed in detail in my forthcoming report on the excavations at Sirjan.

⁹⁹ Ibn Kh., p. 49.

¹⁰⁰ Archaeological survey 1971.

¹⁰¹ opi.cit., note 86.

¹⁰² Stein, "Persis", pp. 190-194.

¹⁰³ opi. cit. in note 87.

¹⁰⁴The excavator's claim that Bīshāpūr was "une citée ouverte" (R. Girshman, Fouilles de Chapour I, p. 29), without military protection does not stand up to the evidence on the ground. To the west the city was protected by the deeply cut bank of the Shāhpūr River, on the north it sheltered beneath the massive masonry of the citadel, and recent excavations has shown that a thick city wall with closely spaced towers provided a secondary defence. On the south and east there has been no excavation, but a great bank still towers up to 8 metres above a wide defensive ditch. Excavations have been carried out at Bīshāpūr since 1968 on behalf of the Iranian Archaeological Service. See A. A. Safaraz, Iran VIII, p. 178; J. Yasi, "The Excavations at Bīshāpūr", Iran IX, 1971, p. 168. I am grateful to Mr. Safaraz for his hospitality at Bīshāpūr.

¹⁰⁵D. B. Whitehouse in David Whitehouse and Andrew Williamson, "Sasanian Maritime Trade", Iran XI, 1973, pp., pp. 33-35.

¹⁰⁶Yahyā, pp. 6, 7.

¹⁰⁷See Appendix 2.

¹⁰⁸e.g. the "central mound" at Tepe Dasht-i Deh of the 13th to 14th centuries. See Andrew Williamson, "Sirjan-i-Kuhna and Tepe Dasht-i-Deh", Excavations in Iran, The British Contribution, Organizing Committee of the VIth International Congress of Iranian Art & Archaeology, Oxford, 1972, pp. 26-28.

¹⁰⁹Firdausī V, p. 268ff.

¹¹⁰Chabot, p. 285. Marquart, Erānshahr, p. 27, considered it as a town.

¹¹¹Firdausī, VI, p. 359 quoted; VI, p. 309; VI 191. For Khusrāu's activities, II, p. 251. The Balūch and Gufṣ even appear under Kei Kavus! ! The tribes are discussed in detail by Marquart, Catalogue, pp. 74-81.

¹¹²Noeldeke, p. 260; Marquart, Erānshahr, p. 42

¹¹³Chabot, pp. 273, 482. Identifications, Noeldeke in Tabarī, p. 57, Bibby, p. 315; Marquart, Erānshahr, p. 43 et. alia.

¹¹⁴The "Seleucid" at Bahrain probably extends into the Parthian period, and perhaps later. The Danish Expedition recognized no Sasanian material from any site. (See Appendix I).

¹¹⁵Chabot, pp. 480, 482.

116 Hamd Allāh Mustaufī, Nuzhat al-Gulūb, trans. G. Le Strange, London 1919, p. 146.

117 J. S. Assemani, Syrus Maronita, Rome 1719-1728, III, pp. 147-148.

118 Survey 1969-1971.

119 Survey 1969.

120 Discovered by Miss B. de Cardi in 1972, personal communication.

121 The evidence for pearling in the Gulf is discussed in Chapter 10.

122 I have been invited to Qatar in 1973 to examine the evidence there.

123 See Chapters 10 and 12.

124 The geographical background is discussed in Chapter 3 above and Chapter 7 below.

125 For the Sasanian material at Sirāf see David Whitehouse, "Siraf a Sasanian Port", Antiquity XLV, 1971, pp. 262-267; Whitehouse in David Whitehouse and Andrew Williamson, "Sasanian Maritime Trade" Iran XI, 1973, pp. 53-55.

126 The solidus is illustrated in Siraf V, pl. XIIIa. A coin of Theodosius I (378-394) from the surface is illustrated in Siraf IV, pl. VIIb.

127 I am grateful to Dr. Whitehouse for discussing the Sasanian evidence from Siraf.

128 Survey 1970.

129 D. Whitehouse survey, Shirinū Kiln 6, personal communication. Stein, Recon., p. 202.

130 The methods for measuring the size of archaeological sites are discussed in Chapter 2.

131 Archaeological survey 1969-1971.

132 9th and 10th century Basra was found on survey in 1971 to occupy almost 3,000 hectares!!

133 The mudflats (known as sabkha, or Persian sabakhzār) stand above mean sea level, but are liable to inundation by unusually high tides, especially when there is a strong wind.

134. Water level in wells used today for irrigation varied from 3.5 metres to 14.6 metres below surface.
135. The route (at that time going to Ganāva) is given in Iṣṭakhrī, p. 131.
136. Ibn al-Balkhī, "Description of Fārs", trans. G. Le Strange, J.R.A.S. 1912, p. 329.
137. Persian Gulf Pilot, 1st edition, London 1865, pp. 204-205.
138. M. Pezard, Mission à Bender Bouchir, M.D.P. XV, 1914, p. 36. A. T. Wilson, The Persian Gulf, London 1928, pp. 73-74, but cf. Stein, Recon., p. 241
139. Barbara English, John Company's Last War, London 1971, pp. 87-88. thought that the fort was built by the Dutch c. 1760.
140. Ibid.
141. Arrian Indica XXIX.1.
142. Not even the great temple at Masjid-i Sulayman is built of fully dressed stones. Iran X, p. 171 and Iran, IX, pp. 173-174 and plates.
143. Bahrain Historical and Archaeological Society, Antiquities of Bahrain, n.d., pp. 15-17. The fullest account of the Hellenistic material from Falaika appears in Anan., "Archaeological Investigations in Falaika, 1958-1964", Kuwait, n.d., Arabic text.
144. R. Girshman, Fouilles de Chāpour, I; Stein, "Persis", pp. 114-122.
145. The evidence for estimating population of archaeological sites is discussed in Chapter 2.
146. L. Lockhart, EI, 2nd edition, art. "Bushahr" and J. Hansman, personal communication.
147. Kārnama, trans. p. 20 refers to its translation.
148. A. T. Wilson, The Persian Gulf, London 1928, p. 73; Hasan, p. 62; E. Streck, EI (1st edition) art. "Būshir"; L. Lockhart, EI, (2nd edition) "Būshahr". E. S. Waring, A Tour to Sheeraz, 1807, is quoted by Wilson, p. 74, writes of Rīshahr, "Pieces of cannon and human images cut in stone have been occasionally found among the ruins of this place."

- 149^{G.} Hüsing, "Elamisches", Z.D.M.G. LVI, 1902, p. 792. For Kiririsha, see W. Hinz, C.A.H. 2nd edition, I(2), pp. 663-664.
- 150^{Tabarī,} p. 820; Noeldeke, p. 19; Hamza, p. 47.
- 151^{Tabarī,} p. 836; Noeldeke, p. 54.
- 152^{Chabot,} p. 285, inter.alia.. Nestorian activity in the Indian Ocean is discussed below.
- 153^{J. St. Martin,} Mémoires historiques et géographiques sur l'Arménie, Paris, 1819, p. 372, trans., p. 373; Marquart, Erānshahr, pp. 138 and 147.
- 154^{Yāqūt,} Mu^cjam al-Buldān, trans. C. B. de Meynard, Dictionnaire Géographique, Historique et Littéraire de la Perse, Paris 1861, p. 271.
- 155^{Balādhurī,} p. 128.
- 156^{Göbl,} p. 84; D. J. Paruck, "Mint Marks of Sasanian and Arab-Sasanian Coins", J.N.S.I. VI, 1944, pp. 111, 121, types 104 and 171.
- 157^{Hamza,} p. 47.
- 158^{Istakhrī,} B.G.A. i, p. 119; Maqdisī, B.G.A. iii, p. 426.
- 159^{Maqdisī,} p. 453.
- 160^{Ibn al-Balkhī,} "Description of the Province of Fārs", trans. G. Le Strange, J.R.A.S., 1912, p. 866.
- 161^{E. Quatremère,} Mémoires Géographiques et Historiques sur l'Égypte et sur quelques contrées voisines, Paris, 1811, p. 284. A. T. Wilson, The Persian Gulf, London 1928, pp. 73-74.
- 162^{Noeldeke,} p. 19; Marquart, Erānshahr, p. 147.
- 163^{See especially} Baladhuri, p. 387, trans., p. 128.
- 164^{The evidence for the location of Tawaj is summarized by} Le Strange, pp. 259-260.
- 165^{Schwarz,} Iran im Mittelalter, pp. 120-121.
- 166^{Chris,} p. 418 and map facing p. 560; Pigul, map facing p. 15; Göbl, map facing p. 100.
- 167^{Hasan,} p. 62; M. Streck, EI (1st edition), art. "Būshir"; L. Lockhart, EI (2nd edition), art. "Būshahr"; A. T. Wilson, The Persian Gulf, London 1928, p. 73.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- Abū Zayd= Abū Zayd in Relations des voyages faits par les Arabes et les Persans dans l'Inde et la Chine dans le IX^e siècle de l'ère chrétienne, ed. Langles, trans. M. Reinaud, Paris 1945.
- ^cAjaib=Buzurg of Ramhurmuz, Kitāb ^cajaib al-Hind, ed. and trans. P. A. van der Lith and Marcel Devic, Livre des merveilles de l'Inde, Leiden 1883-1886.
- Akhbār= 'Ahbār aṣ-Ṣīn wa l'Hind, ed. and trans. Jean Sauvaget, Relation de la Chine et de l'Inde, Paris 1948.
- Amm Marc=Amianus Marcellinus, Res Gestae, trans. J. C. Rolfe, Loeb Classical Library nos. 300, 315, 343, London 1935-1939.
- Balādhurī=al-Balādhurī, Kitāb Futūh al-Buldān, ed. M. J. de Goeje, Leiden 1866; trans. F. C. Murgotten, New York 1924.
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